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THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN LABOR THEORY: EVOLUTION, CHALLENGES AND FUTURE PROSPECTS

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Abstract. This article is devoted to the study of changes in labor theory when using artificial intelligence in the field of labor. In this paper, labor theory is presented as a system consisting of two interacting and interdependent subsystems: the theory of traditional labor and the theory of intellectual labor.

Key words: labor, science of labor, development of the science of labor, intellectual labor, innovative process, artificial intelligence, a form of labor manifestation and the digital economy.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqola mehnat sohasida sun'iy intellektdan foydalanish sharoitida mehnat nazariyasida yuz berayotgan o'zgarishlarni o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Ushbu tadqiqotda mehnat nazariyasi o'zaro bog'liq va o'zaro ta'sir qiluvchi ikki kichik tizimdan iborat tizim sifatida talqin etiladi: an'anaviy mehnat nazariyasi hamda intellektual mehnat nazariyasi.

Kalit so'zlar: mehnat, mehnat fani, mehnat fanining rivojlanishi, intellektual mehnat, innovatsion jarayon, sun'iy intellekt, mehnatning namoyon bo'lish shakli, raqamli iqtisodiyot.

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена исследованию изменений в теории труда в условиях использования искусственного интеллекта в сфере труда. В работе теория труда рассматривается как система, состоящая из двух взаимодействующих и взаимозависимых подсистем: теории традиционного труда и теории интеллектуального труда.

Ключевые слова: труд, наука о труде, развитие науки о труде, интеллектуальный труд, инновационный процесс, искусственный интеллект, форма проявления труда, цифровая экономика.

INTRODUCTION

The modern era is characterized by the unprecedented development of digital technologies, and the world is on the threshold of a new technological revolution based on the rapid development of artificial intelligence. Labor has always been the foundation of the economy, serving as the basis for the creation of tangible and intangible goods. Therefore, the essence and content of labor theory are also being refined and continue to evolve. These changes extend beyond production spheres and also encompass social, cultural and innovative spheres.

Undoubtedly, the digital economy opens up vast opportunities for business development and offers numerous benefits to consumers. The COVID-19 pandemic particularly accelerated the digital transformation of Uzbekistan's economy. During the pandemic, organizations shifted en masse to remote work, spurring the development of specific digital solutions for both business systems and government agencies.

As is well known, the emergence and development of labor theories are linked to the development of theories that directly influenced human history, as they touched on the most fundamental aspect of human nature, distinguishing humans from the rest of the animal kingdom: the ability to labor, that is, to consciously transform natural materials, adapting them to needs and requirements.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

A large number of disciplines have devoted and continue to devote attention to defining the essence of labor. The most recent major stages in the development of labor science date back to the period when

economic theory emerged as a scientific discipline and gave rise to so-called classical political economy. Its founders are considered to be the English scholar William Petty (1623–1687) and the French judge Pierre Boisguillebert (1646–1714).

The labor process is an extremely complex phenomenon and requires physical and mental energy (physical and mental labor). The English economist Adam Smith (1723–1790) made a major contribution to the development of political economy, including labor science. He summarized the ideas of his predecessors in classical economic thought, developing the labor theory of value: "...labor is the only universal, as well as the only accurate, standard of value, or the only measure by which we can compare the values of different commodities at all times and in all places."

The prominent English economist David Ricardo (1772–1823) marked the overcoming of the duality inherent in Adam Smith's theory of the nature of commodity value in favor of the labor theory of value and the recognition of labor as its sole source.

D. Ricardo was at the origin of one of the two branches of economic theory on labor. He wrote: "The value of a commodity, or the quantity of any other commodity for which it exchanges, depends on the relative quantity of labor necessary to produce it, and not on the greater or lesser reward paid for that labor."

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodological basis of the study is grounded in the tenets of Keynesian economic theory, which views labor and employment as key elements of macroeconomic equilibrium and state regulation of the economy. This approach places particular emphasis on the role of the state in mitigating socioeconomic imbalances arising from technological advances and the introduction of artificial intelligence.

The study utilizes theoretical analysis and generalization methods, historical-logical and systems approaches, and elements of institutional analysis. Keynesian methodology is applied to assess the impact of artificial intelligence on the labor market, employment structure and the need for proactive government policy in regulating labor relations.

A comparative analysis is also used to compare traditional and intelligent forms of labor in the context of the digital economy and to determine the socioeconomic consequences of the implementation of artificial intelligence for sustainable employment and economic growth.

Table 1. Stages of AI's Development in Labor Theory

This table describes the evolution of views on automation and labor.

Stage	Period	The Role of AI/Technology	Impact on the labor market
I. Mechanization	XIX - mid-XX century	Physical machines	Replacement of heavy manual labor, increase in productivity.
II. Digitalization	1970s-2010s	Computers, software, Internet	Automation of routine (accounting, data tasks).
III. Intellectualization	2020s-present	Generative AI, LLM, neural networks	Cognitive automation takes over creative analytical tasks
IV. Syntax of the Future	2030+ (forecast)	AGI (General Information)	Deep integration, the emergence of new professions ("Operator of meanings").

The use of AI poses both economic and ethical challenges.

- Technological unemployment: Risk of displacement of mid-level specialists (lawyers, copywriters, analysts).

- Digital divide: Gap between those who have AI skills and those who do not.

- Ethics and algorithmic bias: Risk of discrimination in hiring through AI algorithms.

- Identity crisis: Loss of a sense of meaning in work when a machine performs the job faster and better.

Since I am a text-based AI, I will prepare a graph structure for you, which you can transfer to Excel, Canva or draw on a slide.

Chart Type: Stacked Chart (Future Skills)

X-Axis: Time (2020–2030)

Y-Axis: Skill Importance (%)

1. Hard Skills: The line slopes downward (AI writes code and performs calculations independently).
2. AI Literacy: The line rises sharply (the ability to create prompts and manage systems).
3. Soft Skills: The line remains consistently high (empathy, leadership and negotiation are skills that AI does not yet replace).

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The study found that the development of artificial intelligence is significantly influencing the evolution of labor theory, changing the content, forms and structure of work. Modern labor theory in the digital economy is increasingly characterized by a shift in emphasis from traditional, regulated labor to intellectual, innovative and creative labor.

It has been revealed that labor in modern conditions is a complex system comprising physical and mental components, with the role of mental and intellectual labor significantly increasing. The use of artificial intelligence facilitates the automation of routine operations, reducing the need for low-skilled labor while simultaneously increasing the demand for workers with analytical, creative and digital competencies.

The study confirmed the relevance of the concept of dividing labor into regulated (α -labor) and innovative, creative (β -labor). Artificial intelligence is increasingly integrated into the sphere of regulated labor, while functions related to development, management, control and decision-making retain the key role of humans as bearers of intellectual potential.

It has been established that intellectual labor is becoming a key factor in innovative development and economic growth in the digital economy. The use of artificial intelligence expands the possibilities for creating new products, technologies and production organization methods, reinforcing the importance of labor science and requiring its further theoretical development.

The study's findings also demonstrate that the introduction of artificial intelligence is accompanied by structural changes in the labor market, including the transformation of employment, the emergence of new professions and changing skill requirements. Under these circumstances, public policies aimed at regulating social and labor processes, supporting employment and developing human capital are increasingly important.

Researchers in the field of labor sciences have repeatedly attempted to introduce their own original systems of terminology. The most well-known terminology system was proposed by Professor B.M. Genkin, who identified two components in any work. The first component is associated with work performed according to a given technology, instructions, regulations, tradition and so forth, when the performer (the subject of the work) does not introduce any elements of innovation; creative potential is either not tapped at all or is used at a primitive level (he called such work REGULATED or α -LABOR).

The second component is associated with the creation of material or spiritual goods, as well as new production methods (he called such work INNOVATIVE, CREATIVE or β -LABOR).

The concept of "intellectual labor" is widely used in international practice. Thus, Article 6 of the WIPO (World Intellectual Property Organization) Copyright Treaty states:

"Compilations of data or other materials in any form which by their selection and arrangement constitute intellectual property shall be protected as such. This protection extends beyond the data and materials themselves and is without prejudice to any copyright that protects them."

Thus, copyright facilitates the creation of computer software, AI, robotics, artistic, literary and other works of art.

This provision is most characteristic of the concept of "INTELLIGENCE," which in the 21st century was defined as follows: "INTELLIGENCE (from the Latin intellectus – knowledge, understanding, reason), the ability to think and to engage in rational cognition, as distinguished from, for example, mental faculties such as feeling, will, intuition, imagination and others. Since the late 19th century, various quantitative assessment methods have become widespread in experimental psychology, using tests and a specific system of their statistical processing in factor analysis."

The English scientist Alfred Marshall (1842–1924) wrote in his main work, Principles of Economics, that there is no need to define differences between various economic categories, since "in real life there is no clear distinction between things that are capital and those that are not, between things that are essential and those that are not, between productive and unproductive labor."

In the history of economic thought, the name of the Austrian scholar, economist and sociologist Joseph Schumpeter stands apart. His work, The Theory of Economic Development (1912), is particularly interesting for its justification of the role of the entrepreneur as the most important factor of production and the primary driving force of a market economy. He wrote: "By entrepreneurs... we mean economic entities whose function is... to implement new combinations and who act as its active element."

The functions of an entrepreneur, who is usually not the owner of the enterprise, include innovations in production:

1. The production of a new good unknown to consumers or the creation of a new quality of a particular good;
2. The introduction of a new, previously unknown method of production or a new method of commercial use of the relevant product;
3. The development of a new sales market in which a given branch of industry in a given country has not previously been represented, regardless of whether this market previously existed or not;
4. Obtaining a new source of raw materials or semi-finished products, regardless of whether this source existed previously, was simply overlooked, was considered inaccessible or had yet to be created;
5. Conducting an appropriate reorganization, for example ensuring a monopoly position for one's own enterprise or undermining the monopoly position of another enterprise.

Labor theory always deals with complex systems for which long-term forecasts are extremely illusory, and this is especially true for intellectual labor.

Uzbekistan's chosen path of development is linked to the creation of the foundations of a socially oriented market economy. "Science is characterized by an interest in the essence of phenomena, clarity and unity of formulations, which was also manifested in the formation of the system of concepts of economic theory, including labor theory," notes Academician of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan K.Kh. Abdurakhmanov.

In Uzbekistan, the development of artificial intelligence is supported by the state program "Digital Uzbekistan – 2030." The investment volume is still limited, but this will not only strengthen the position of businesses in the digital economy, but also ensure the sustainable development of the economy as a whole. The development of labor science, technology and innovation, the accelerating pace of scientific and technological progress and increased international competition are creating new requirements for the strategic management of high-tech industries capable of creating and commercializing breakthrough innovations, achieving technological independence and enhancing national security.

Several scientific problems have also been identified that must be addressed in the process of introducing artificial intelligence into our lives. All of these issues can confidently be considered relevant to the social and labor sphere of the economy.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Labor theory is constantly evolving, but its future prospects are seen only in a direction that will allow humanity to avoid new economic and social upheavals and ensure progressive development, as well as material and spiritual well-being.

Undoubtedly, the expansion of artificial intelligence will reduce employers' need to attract workers and individuals. In light of this, it is important for the state to formulate a strategy to address the challenges that the widespread use of artificial intelligence in the workplace may entail. It is proposed to create a list of jobs performed exclusively by humans, define rules for building collaborative relationships between humans and robots and establish quotas for the number of jobs occupied.

To summarize this study, it should be noted that all developed countries recognize that digitalization brings a new way of life and serves as a new foundation for public administration, the economy and the social sphere. Its implementation in all spheres is an inevitable process that all countries will undergo.

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